

Identifying The Students' Motivation to Learn Writing

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ABSTRAK

The attempt to identify the student's motivation towards English has been extensively studied. However, identifying the students learning to write in relation to employment is scarcely conducted. In fact, writing skill has been postulated as the most challenging and rewarding skill to acquire future employment. The present study was conducted qualitatively. The reason for using qualitative was the limited time and sources that the researcher had. The sources of data were taken from the students who are currently studying in an English department, where the researcher is working as one of their English lecturers. There were 10 participants who were recruited randomly and voluntarily. The application of random sampling was aimed to allow the participants to freely and conveniently participate in the study. The instrument employed was an open-ended interview. The data analysed was the participants' verbal responses delivered during the interviews. The finding indicated that learning to write was both important and challenging for them. With regard to the students' future, learning to write was perceived important for students as they had to compete with the other university graduates to secure a decent employment. They thought that being an English graduate was not viewed from the way they communicate orally but more on the way to create formal impression through written media in which they are using

to find jobs. Besides, the potential migration of the students to other English speaking countries is also perceived as the other primary reason for the student to acquire this skill. Since their motivation to learn English was instrumental and not integrative, despite planning to stay overseas, they considered that there were more aspects that should be done through writing rather than speaking. For instance, when dealing with documents and making reports they should rely on their writing skill rather than other skills.

PENDAHULUAN

Humans need to communicate in order to survive and to continue their civilization. However, as the time goes, the way to communicate is not always in oral manner. The rise of internet, for instance, has driven people to communicate without being limited by space and time (Klimova, 2014). Nowadays, people can communicate without any border. The rise of social media and internet has driven people to create more unique ways to communicate; thus creating written means is important.

Despite being used in more informal manner, the use of writing has been able to penetrate more people worldwide. In fact, the use of more icons has also increased the beautification of written languages in social media. The way people write nowadays has become an important message which arouses others' attraction thus allowing the writer to socialize more extensively. The role of motivation in English education or pedagogical aspects has been extensively studied (Erizar, 2019; Purnama et al., 2019; Azar & Tanggaraju, 2020; Kruk, 2022; Amelia et al., 2024). Despite being important these studies, do not touch the most common issue, which most young generations encounter.

In fact, most of the students studying in colleges or universities are nowadays struggling hard to secure an employment after graduation. This fact has also been considered important for the administrators or college managements. The acceptance of their graduates in employment will directly increase the image of the universities. In sum, finding jobs is not only the obligation of the graduates but also the colleges. Admittedly, studies regarding the role of English in employment are scarcely identified. There are very few studies, which are identified in relation to employment (See e.g., Evans, 2010; Kamlun, 2020; Alamsyah et al., 2024). In fact, the need to find jobs is getting more imperative as there are more challenges to find jobs at the moments. The slump of the economy, the global virus infection, and the rising conflicts between superpower countries have triggered millions of people migrate for safety (International Organization for Migration, 2024).

The need to identify the reasons for people to learn English, particularly in writing is important. Previous studies have shown that more employers nowadays tend to demand the applicants to have effective communication ability, and not only speaking ability (Ting et al., 2017). Further studies also

indicated that more employers are increasingly demanding their workers to write more effectively during their daily works (Steven, 2005). The present study aimed to examine the students' views on their learning to write and its potential impact to their future employment.

The study was conducted only in a small scope within the lecturer's working context. Specifically, the sample was taken from a class in which the researcher taught in the previous semester. In sum, this study was conducted in a privately funded university in which the researcher is working as a lecturer. The result of the study might be different when the research is conducted in a different university in which the researcher has no potential connection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Motivation to learn a foreign language

Scholars have long postulated that motivation is a trigger for humans to do something. In terms of foreign language learning, Suliman, et al., (2024) corroborate that motivation is inseparable in supporting the learning process. However, in a more comprehensive outlook, motivation is not only considered as a drive to do something. Cook and Artino (2016) define motivation as the process in which the goal-directed activities are initiated and sustained. From this paradigm, the concept of motivation has at least two aspects: Firstly, the goal which directs someone to do something and the sustainability allowing the doer to do consistently.

Denarti and Damayanti (2023) identified that the students they researched had both intrinsic and extrinsic elements when learning English. However, they also identified that those who had higher scores in English tended to have relatively lower motivation. It means that the correlation between those having higher and their motivation is not very significant.

Employment, foreign language mastery, and prosperity

Scholars have long postulated that there is a close relationship between foreign language mastery and employment. In European context, Araújo et al., (2015) have identified that mastering foreign language skills, such as English, German, and other languages might significantly affect the opportunity to get employment. Likewise, in Asian context, Nghia et al. (2024) identifies that English language skill is very important in Vietnam employment.

It has been admitted that most of English speaking countries tend to have more prosperity index compared with non-English speaking countries for instance the countries like America, Britain, and Australia belong to developed countries. On the other hand those who learn English mostly come from developing countries. It is also a common phenomenon that those who learn English will typically immigrate or plan to study in English speaking countries.

Skills in English

There is a commonly perceived division in a language: reading, listening, speaking, and writing. Harmer (2007) perceived that reading and listening belong to a receptive learning. On the other hand, speaking, and writing belong to productive learning. In this case, this concept tends to categorize that receptive belongs to learning process in which the learners will generally receive the information, while productive learning tends to categorize the skills as a means in which the students will have to produce the activity.

METHOD

Research design

Merriam (as cited in Barrale, 2017, p. 39) postulates that qualitative study allows the researchers to portray the participant's experience and other relevant aspects pertaining to their experience. Specifically, the researcher employed a case study so that the researcher could possibly delve into the most possible information relevant to their focus of the study. Yin (2014) defines a case study as "an empirical inquiry which investigates a contemporary phenomenon (the case) in depth within its real-world context, especially when the boundaries between phenomenon and context may not be clearly evident". Furthermore, Yin (2014) elaborates that case study method is suitable for some considerations, such as the focus of the study is to answer "How" and "Why" and the absence of manipulation conducted to the respondents or participants being studied.

Number of participants

There were ten participants who were recruited voluntarily for the study. The adoption of voluntary aspect was to allow the participant of having more freedom when participating in the interview. Prior to the application of the interview the participant was given the information on the importance of the study and the potential relevance to their study. The information given enabled the participant to think the potential relevance and benefit for them when they participated into the program. Based on the

information given to the participants, there were ten students who stated their willingness to participate in the study. The participants were listed in the table below:

No	Age	Occupations	Gender
1	18	Cashier	Female
2	19	Factory worker	Female
3	20	Teacher	Male
4	19	Marketing officer	Female
5	20	On-line marketing	Male
6	19	Unemployed	Male
7	22	Unemployed	Female
8	18	Teacher	Female
9	18	Teacher	Male
10	19	Unemployed	Female

Instruments

The instrument used in the study was interview. Interview was considered more relevant to dig up more information and is not limited by the researcher. Specifically, the interview is categorized as an open-ended interview, which means that the interview is not limited into some categories/limitations. The use of open-ended will allow the participants to fully express their thoughts/minds pertaining to the questions directed to them.

Sources of data

Data is any means of information given by the respondent during the research (Frankel, Wallen, & Hyun, 2012). The data elicited in the study was the participants' verbal responses given during the interviews and were considered relevant to the questions directed to them.

Data collection procedure

The data collection procedure was conducted as the followings: firstly, the researcher distributed some notices regarding the information on the research project; the importance of the research for the institutions, researcher, and the students; the schedule proposed for the research; and the right of the participants when taking part in the project. The researcher adopted the random sampling in order to allow the researchers to recruit anyone who was willing to the project. After the recruitment of the participants, the researcher briefed the participants on the proposed research project. The researcher also offered the participants the chance to ask for clarification to ensure that they had already grasped the whole interview items. The interview was conducted in the participants' native language. The interview was recorded to maintain the naturalness of the data. The result of the recorded interview was also confronted by the participants. The analysis of the verbal data was conducted using theme analysis (Creswell, 2008).

Given the potential limitation on the use of a single instrument in the present study, the researcher adopted some of the steps conducted by Barrale (2017, p. 41), such as allowing the participants to provide more clarification to the researcher, multiple interviews/follow up interviews when needed, etc.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The participants' views on writing skill

No	Verbal Responses
1	I think writing is important but it is also the most difficult skill that I learn in English department. Mostly about the grammar that should be very accurate and lots of words that I must depend on writing..
2	I think I need to write although it is difficult I think I have to do it. Speaking in English or other foreign languages is very common nowadays. Almost all of university students know English.
3	As a teacher, I must be able to write, so writing is important and I need to learn to write.
4	I need to learn to write. But, here, the topic is always the same, and the emphasis is mostly on grammar not on the topic you write. The lecturer focuses on the clarity and accuracy, but unfortunately they don't seem interested in the real writing needed by the worker like me.
5	I think writing is difficult the teacher should find the way to help us improve our writing.
6	Writing is important but speaking is also important.

7	I think speaking is important as people will see you for the first time from speaking, so I believe speaking is more important than writing.
8	I think writing is important but it is a complicated skill. It takes more than one aspects. So, you need to have more words, and grammar, and practice to help improve your writing.
9	Writing is more difficult than other skills in English.
10	I don't like writing. I hope that I don't need to write my thesis in English so I just write in Indonesian language. It is hard to write lots of pages in English.

Participants' view on the importance of writing skill in acquiring employment

No	Verbal Responses
1	As a cashier I definitely need to speak anytime with the customers who buy things in the shop, but sometimes I need to write to make report. I find it hard to write.
2	Although I work as a factory worker, I constantly work on written procedure in English. It means I need to read and sometimes rewrite some procedures. For me speaking is not difficult as what we speak is very simple. But, the problem is when I have to re-write the procedure in English as I have to explain it to the boss or the manager. I need to re-write because I should not take all the real procedure to be memorized. So, writing is important for me. I heard working abroad or is more rewarding so I hope I can work overseas in the same industries.
3	As a teacher, I still hope to have better skill in English. I wish I can work abroad. Working as a teacher at the moment doesn't pay you much. I continuously share my CV to many people and social media. I also share some activities in English to my colleagues abroad. I hope they will be interested and recruit me to work abroad or somewhere else which pays me better than now.
4	As a marketing officer, I continuously present and deliver lots of papers, cards, or small notices in English to the prospective buyers. I do not talk to them directly. Although, when we are in the stand, we meet some of them, they sometimes can speak Indonesian so we can speak Indonesian language. But, the flyers or other commercial notices are usually written in English and in Indonesian language. Working abroad? Why not, I have travelled to some Asian countries, so I think writing is more important for me. I speak anytime and it is not difficult.
5	As an on-line marketer I constantly share some words, phrases, or sentences in English to provoke the readers or those who search the products or those who are on-line to be curious. The use of words, or phrases, which are funny or interesting, or sometimes rather unique, can make the people to be curious and see our products. I hope my contact with some foreigners will make me work abroad. So, I need to constantly create more impressive writing and text in English to promote me and my products.
6	I don't depend on my writing when I search for a job, as I usually visit the factory or offices. But, nowadays, searching for jobs will require you to share to send through e-mail, so when sending the e-mail or some documents, you will have to write in English. Again, when we apply through the web we need to depend on our writing skill to create good impression.
7	I don't write well, and I just speak. I hope to improve and to work better. Now, I depend on my friend's help to write my CV and other document to apply for a job. Yes, it is a must to write a good CV or application letter to make the boss interested to call you.
8	As a teacher for children, I don't write much, I usually speak more often, however, in the future, when I teach adult I might need to write as they will probably work or having some important positions, which require them to

	write reports.
9	I teach elementary school students, so I usually use LKS or some small books given to me from school and we constantly use these books to help students, so mostly we learn to read, and read. But there are times to write and to summarize the ideas from the reading text.
10	I hope I can get a job soon. I don't know what skill I should rely on. I hope, I can meet the boss or the manager easily in the factory. But, nowadays, we don't communicate directly, but we send through e-mail. So, it is a faceless communication and we need to depend on writing skill.

Analysis

The fierce competition in acquiring a decent employment

The findings indicate that most of the activities in applying for a job nowadays are no longer a physical action. In fact, it is all conducted through e-mail and almost without physical contacts. Creating good impression through writing is necessary. It is definitely important to help the students to attract the potential employers to call for an interview.

This finding is relevant to numerous scholars who have identified the important role of social media in facilitating the application process. Therefore, it is important to note that the applications should be able to cater a very well-documented text. This newly adopted application has finally driven the written communication. Scholars identify that nowadays most people prefer to communicate more through written means than oral forms as it allows them to reach much larger audience (See, for example, Klimova, 2014; Belal, 2014). Based on this argument, Olsthain (2001) predicts that writing skill that is supported with a globally accepted language constitutes an essential means of communication in today's world (Olsthain, 2001).

The possible migration or working abroad

The findings also indicated that the motivation to learn English is to migrate abroad as stated by some of the participants. The importance of acquiring writing skill is definitely sensible. The requirements to prepare the documents and to write accurately in English are important as they need to have office working position abroad. In more complete argument, Adserà, and Pytliková (2016) elaborate that language proficiency is essential for international migrants. Better proficiency will allow them to assimilate and socialize in the host countries and allow them to participate in employment sectors. The difficulties in having more vocabulary and accurate grammar are the most essential challenges

The findings are definitely relevant to numerous scholars' arguments which indicate the difficulties of writings. Richards and Renandya (2004) confirm that writing is the most complex skill students have to acquire. It requires the students to notice various aspects of their writing skills. They further elaborate that the challenges in learning to write may not only come from generating and organizing ideas but also from interpreting these ideas into readable texts (Richards & Renandya, 2004, p. 303). In sum, when learning to write, students will be faced with many aspects, such as vocabulary, grammar mastery, spelling, readiness, and sufficient exposure to books and relevant reading materials (Moses & Mohamad, 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

English has been popular and continuously will be needed worldwide. However, the emphasis of the teaching in the future employment should be changed. Given the currently dynamic situation driving people to survive and to create more networks to defend their lives, there should be more emphasis on the formal aspects of English in which this language will be useful in the future. For instance, the teaching should be based on the current demand in employment in which most of the employers require the workers to communicate effectively and not only to master a language to speak.

In fact, the need to master writing will also be important since more formal occasions will require people or those attend in these important moments to jot down the precious aspects pertaining to the occasions. Finally, the need to work and live overseas will also require more than just speaking. In fact, the graduates must also be able to deliver precise information, which are mostly delivered through formal channel, namely writing.

SUGGESTIONS

Despite highlighting important relationship between writing skill and employment, further studies should also considered the present study's limitations, which are briefly explained below:

- a) The students who participated in the study were the ones studying in the course taught by the researcher in the university. Therefore, despite being given preliminary information on the proposed

projects and other good research practices, the potential relationship between the students and the lecturer might arise and lead to certain bias. Further study might entail more objective and independent study, in which the context of study should not be connected to the researcher's job or profession.

- b) The analysis was supported by sources of data taken from a single instrument, namely open-ended interview. Therefore, despite having ample chances to the researcher to elicit more verbal responses, potentially partial meaning from the participants' perspective might arise. Further study should involve more triangulation or other supporting instruments so that the data will be more valid and dependable.

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